

HUMAN VALUE IS THE MOST VALUABLE

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Abstract. This article provided information about the glorification of human dignity and the various reforms carried out in our country today for human value and their effectiveness.

Keywords: New Uzbekistan, human dignity, Action Strategy, Development Strategy, principle "for Human Dignity", law, decree, value, upbringing.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada inson qadrini ulug'lash va bugungi kunda mamlakatimizda inson qadri uchun olib borilayotgan turli xil islohotlar va ularning samaralari haqida ma'lumotlar keltirib o'tildi.

Kalit so'zlar: Yangi O'zbekiston, Inson qadri, Harakatlar strategiyasi, Taraqqiyot strategiyasi, "Inson qadri uchun" tamoyili, qonun, farmon, qadriyat, tarbiya.

Аннотация. В данной статье была дана информация о прославлении человеческого достоинства и различных реформах, проводимых сегодня в нашей стране для человеческого достоинства и их результатах.

Ключевые слова: Новый Узбекистан, Человеческая ценность, Стратегия действий, Стратегия развития, принцип «Во имя человеческой ценности», закон, указ, ценность, образование.

INTRODUCTION

Today, New Uzbekistan is being built on the basis of the important idea of "a society with human dignity and a people-friendly state". Based on this ambitious goal set by the head of our state, our nation is becoming the real author of new reforms. In particular, the naming of 2022 as "The Year of Human Dignity and Active Neighborhood" is a vivid example of this. In the new year 2022, the scale of our efforts in our country from the strategy of actions to the strategy of development has intensified. In this, the idea of goodness for human dignity plays an important role. During the next two years, due to the large-scale reforms implemented in our country under the leadership of the Honorable President Shavkat Mirziyoyev to raise the development of Uzbekistan to a new level, fundamental changes are taking place in all aspects, the worldview and consciousness of our people is rising. New values and traditions are being formed in our society. In the following years, Uzbekistan began to be mentioned as a people-loving, humanitarian country. It would be appropriate to show the work being done to support low-income, helpless families and reduce poverty in our country. On New Year's Eve, the state provided new homes for children brought up in Mercy Homes.

Good deeds and good deeds will continue, and the country where human dignity is glorified will always progress. People live in harmony and kindness. Therefore, in the main reforms in our country, great attention is paid to human dignity and dignity.

As we mentioned above, on January 26 of this year, during the meeting of the video selector chaired by the head of our country, regarding the determination of the development strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 and the discussion of its implementation this year, people in our country the tasks of glorifying its value were defined. Therefore, glorifying human dignity is the highest virtue and is a logical continuation of reforms in our country.

The head of our state said, "Human dignity is not an abstract, lofty concept for us. By human dignity, we mean, first of all, the peaceful and safe life of every citizen, the provision of

his fundamental rights and freedoms. By human dignity, we mean the creation of decent living conditions and modern infrastructure for every citizen, provision of qualified medical services, quality education, social protection system, and creation of a healthy ecological environment.

RESEARCH RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In the new era of our development, a practical expression of attention to human value is being formed in the consciousness of our population, especially our youth, and these qualities are becoming more and more firmly established in the lifestyle of our people.

Human value is not some abstract, lofty concept for us. By human dignity, we mean, first of all, the peaceful and safe life of every citizen, the provision of his fundamental rights and freedoms. It is worth noting that the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, adopted 73 years ago, opened new opportunities for the establishment of principles of democracy and humanity in the world. In our country, all measures are being taken to ensure that human rights and freedoms are manifested as the highest value of a democratic society.

When the people agree, the society is peaceful and happy. At a time when everything is sufficient and the value of a person is gradually decreasing, our president is talking about the need to glorify the value of a person, his benefits, his good life, and the need for his family to live peacefully and comfortably.

In our republic, various projects, laws, and decrees regarding human dignity are being developed and they are being implemented. Great attention is being paid to supporting young people, providing them with all opportunities, and shaping them into mature individuals who will benefit the future of the country.

Also, the importance of the above-mentioned development strategy is that in its development, existing problems were taken into account, urgent tasks awaiting solution were reflected. Most importantly, our people actively participated in the development of the document. Literally, it can be said that it was developed under the co-authorship of our people.

The document clearly reflects the task of fully realizing the principle "For human dignity" in life. It should be said that this value is a concept free from lofty words, and at its heart is the peaceful and safe life of every person, the provision of his fundamental rights and freedoms, the establishment of decent living conditions and modern infrastructure for every citizen, the provision of qualified medical services, quality education, priority goals and tasks such as creating a social protection system and a healthy ecological environment are included.

In particular, the Development Strategy and the "roadmap" for its implementation in 2022 envisage the achievement of nearly 100 goals within the 7 priority directions of the development of our country. These are:

1. 41 measures aimed at achieving the following goals in the direction of establishing a people-friendly state by increasing human dignity and further developing a free civil society are defined:

2. In the direction of making the principles of justice and the rule of law the most basic and necessary condition for development in our country, 28 measures aimed at achieving the following goals are defined:

3. 133 measures aimed at achieving the following goals are being determined in the direction of developing the national economy and ensuring its growth rates at the level of modern requirements:

4. 55 measures aimed at achieving the following goals in the direction of conducting a fair social policy and developing human capital are defined:

5. 33 measures aimed at achieving the following goals are defined in the direction of ensuring spiritual development, radical reform of this field and bringing it to a new stage:

6. In the direction of finding solutions to universal problems based on national interests, 39 measures aimed at achieving the following goals are defined:

7. 77 measures aimed at achieving the following goals are being determined in the direction of strengthening the security and defense potential of our country, conducting an open and pragmatic, active foreign policy.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, we can see that today, based on all the laws, decrees and other legal documents that are being developed, the highest goal is aimed at glorifying the human spirit.

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